

TARKIBIDA GLIKOZIDLAR BO'LGAN DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLAR

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada tarkibida glikozidlar bo'lgan dorivor o'simliklar to'g'risidagi bilimlarini boyitish, ulardan to'g'ri foydalanish usullarini o'rganish, amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish. Tarkibida glikozidlar bo'lgan dorivor o'simliklardan uy sharoitida damlama va qaynatmalar tayyorlashni o'rganib olish mumkin.

Ortosifon, buyrak choy (*Orthosiphon stamineus*) yasnotkadoshlar *Lamiaceae* (labguldoshlar — *Labiatae*) oilasiga kiradi.

Ko'p yillik, bo'yi 1—1,5 m ga yetadigan doim yashil yarim buta yoki buta. Bargi oddiy, bandi bilan poyada butsimon shaklda qarama-qarshi o'rnashgan. Mevasi 1—4 ta yong'oqchadan iborat. Iyul-avgust oylarida gullaydi. Vatani Janubi-Sharqiy Osiyoning tropik rayonlari. U yovvoyi holda Indoneziyada (Yava, Sumatra va Borneo orollarida), Birmada, Filippinda va Shimoliy-Sharqiy Avstraliyada o'sadi. Bir yillik o'simlik sifatida Gruziyaning subtropik tumanlarida o'stiriladi. O'simlik qishda oranjereyada saqlanadi. Erta bahorda undan 2 ta bargli novdachalar qirqib olinadi va oranjereyada ko'chat qilib o'tqaziladi. May oyida esa bu ko'chatlar ochiq yerga o'tqaziladi.

Dorivor preparati. Damlama.

Nashasimon kendir (*Apocynum cannabinum*) kendir doshlar — *Apocynaceae* oilasiga kiradi. Nashasimon kendir ko'p yillik, bo'yi 1—1,5 m ga yetadigan o't o'simlik. Ildiz sistemasi yer ostida juda kuchli taraqqiy etgan bo'lib, o'simlikning vegetativ ko'payishida katta ahamiyatga ega. Yer ostida ildizning yuqori qismidan turli tomonga yo'nalgan hamda gorizontal joylashgan yer ostki yotiq novdalar — stolonlar chiqadi. Stolonlar ma'lum yerda yer ustki poya va ildizlar hosil qiladi. Natijada kendir o'simligi bir-biri bilan yer ostida chatishib, bir necha gektarga tarqalib ketadi.

Poyasi tik o'suvchi, yashil yoki to'q qizil rangli bo'lib, qarama-qarshi shoxlangan. Bargi oddiy, lansetsimon yoki cho'ziq tuxumsimon, o'tkir uchli, tekis qirrali, tuksiz poyada qisqa bandi bilan qarama-qarshi, ba'zan ketma-ket o'rnashgan. Gullari ro'vaksimon qalqonga to'plangan.

Gulkosachasi chuqur besh bo'lakka qirqilgan, gultojisi pushti yoki oq, silindrsimon-qo'ng'iroqsimon bo'lib, yarmisiga qadar besh bo'lakka qirqilgan. O'taligi 5 ta, onaligi ikkita meva bargidan tashkil topgan. Mevasi — pishganda ochiladigan bargcha.

Iyun-avgust oylarida gullaydi, mevasi sentabr-oktabrda yetiladi. Bu o'simlik yovvoyi holda Shimoliy Amerikada o'sadi. Moskva viloyati, O'zbekistonda (Toshkent viloyatida) o'stiriladi.

Apocynum cannabinum - nashasimon kendir

Ildizpoya va stolonidan 0,17—0,50% gacha simarin (gidrolizlanganda simaroza kandigav va strofantidin aglikoniga parchalanadi), apokannoqid, sinokannoqid, 0,33% gacha K-strofantin-b va boshqa yurak glikozidlari ajratib olingan. Urugo'ida 0,35%, bargida esa kam miqdorda yurak glikozidlari bor.

Dorivor preparatlari. Simarin standart.

TADQIQOT NATIJALAR

1. Ortosifon o'simligining preparati siydik haydovchi vositasi sifatida buyrak (buyrak tosh kasalligi) hamda xoletsistit va yurak glikozidlari bilan birgalikda yurak qon tomiri sistemasining II - III darajali kasalliklarida ishlatiladi.

2. Nashasimon kendir o'simligining preparatlari yurak kasalliklarida (qon aylanishining II va III darajali buzilishida) ishlatiladi. Bu o'simlik preparatlarini chet mamlakatlardan keltiriladigan strofant o'simligi preparatlari o'rnida ishlatish tavsiya etiladi.

XULOSA

Orthosiphon stamineus - ortosifon, buyrak choy. Mahsulot tarkibida triterpen saponinlar, m-inozit, achchiq ortosifonin glikozidi, 1,5% gacha vino, limon va boshqa kislotalar, 0,2—0,66% efir moyi, 5—6% oshlovchi va boshqa moddalar hamda ko'p miqdorda kaliy tuzlari bo'ladi. Saponinlardan birining anglikoni — sapofanin a-amirin ekanligi aniqlandi.

Apocynum cannabinum - nashasimon kendir

Mahsulot tarkibida 0,8% gacha yurak glikozidlari, tanin, kauchuk, oz miqdorda alkaloidlar, organik kislotalar, triterpen (oleanol kislota, amirin, lupeol va boshqalar) hamda boshqa

birikmalar bo'ladi.

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